

Model Assessment of Potential and Barriers to the Development of Renewable Energy Communities at the National Level

Assessing the Impacts of Energy Communities: An Overview of (Potential) Costs and Benefits (Background Paper #4)

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Abbreviations

AEE	Agentur für Erneuerbare Energien [Renewable Energy Agency, Germany]	IÖW	Institut für ökologische Wirtschaftsforschung [Institute for Ecological Economy Research]
CGE	computable general equilibrium	KPI	key performance indicator
EU	European Union	LM3	local multiplier 3
IAM	integrated assessment model	MS	Member State
IO	input-output	REC	renewable energy community
		SAM	social accounting matrix

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1 Context

An analysis of potential costs and benefits is needed to justify any policy intervention. Moreover, such an assessment of costs and benefits may help to evaluate the choice of different policy instruments. Normally, policy-makers get involved when they know that what they are supporting will have a positive impact. Energy communities themselves may wish to demonstrate the environmental or social benefits that they provide. Hence, they may report not only on their financial results, but also on non-financials, e.g. through a common good balance sheet or key performance indicators (KPIs) according to a sustainability reporting standard. In the following, we focus on the former, not the latter. Therefore, we take the perspective of a policy-maker or an advocacy group, not an energy community organisation. This said, most of the benefits and costs mentioned below can be “translated” into KPIs for energy communities.

Different potential benefits of energy communities compared with non-local forms of ownership have been described in the literature, including conditions that have to be met for these benefits to materialize (Berka & Creamer, 2018). As Berka and Creamer (2018) work out, impacts of energy communities can be assessed using different methods. We follow them in their distinction of

- a) interviews, i.e. qualitative assessments, often based on single or few cases,
- b) surveys, i.e. questionnaires with standardised questions to a (random) selection of respondents, which are analysed by means of statistical methods, and
- c) models, i.e. mostly economic models using techniques such as input-output (IO) analysis, computable general equilibrium (CGE), social accounting matrix (SAM) or local multiplier 3 (LM3).

A proper assessment of (potential) costs and benefits associated with the implementation of certain measures for renewable energy communities (RECs) could be based on an extended version of one of the integrated assessment models (IAMs) in use for energy policy evaluations. However, this would make high demands on additional data and would involve substantial modifications of existing models. The same is true for monetarising non-monetary impacts of RECs in a fully-fledged cost-benefit analysis of specific policies or projects. Hence, we will rather highlight some practical tools and suggest some methods to do a rapid assessment of (gross) benefits and costs from using the REC potential in EU Member States (MS). As we will discuss measures in favour of RECs, the major focus here will be on benefits.

The first step taken is a systematisation of impacts, i.e. costs and benefits, discussed in the literature (Section 2). Using our typology, we will briefly describe findings from the literature on each benefit, including some possible ways to quantify these benefits (Section 3). As Berka and Creamer have highlighted, the empirical evidence for these impacts is relatively scarce, often anecdotal, derived from single case studies, often using qualitative methods of investigation, and sometimes connected to specific types of community energy (Berka & Creamer, 2018). Therefore, we need to take into consideration different types or levels of participation. Moreover, we will include some information on potential intervening factors as discussed in the literature. It is clear from the literature that benefits do not uniformly apply to all kinds of RECs in all cases, but are rather contingent on certain conditions that have to be met.

In addition to this brief overview that builds on existing reviews of the literature, we provide a list of the literature that should become part of the EU energy community repository.

2 Typology of Impacts

There are several papers reviewing the literature on impacts of energy communities (Berka & Creamer, 2018; Busch et al., 2019; Hauser et al., 2015; Hoffmann et al., 2021; Standal et al., 2022). Typologies differ in detail, but have major elements in common. We organize our typology according to three rationales commonly ascribed to political participation: improved effectiveness, emancipation and higher legitimacy (Newig & Koontz, 2014; Newig & Kvarda, 2012). We assign all (potential) impacts of energy communities to one of these three rationales. We briefly list the potential impacts here (see also Figure 1) and discuss them in some more details in the following chapter.

Energy communities may improve **effectiveness** in various ways:

- Energy communities mobilise money and space/land. On the negative side, support programmes for energy communities cost money that could otherwise be used alternatively.
- Projects implemented by energy communities can have beneficial (or detrimental) environmental effects, especially on greenhouse gas emissions.

- A major technological aspect are effects on grids. Distributed energy technologies from RECs (as well as other market actors) can relieve the existing grid or possibly also place an additional burden on it. Furthermore, they may have an impact on the (future) grid expansion.
- Participation in an energy community may influence the behaviour of members, especially on electricity consumption.
- The literature describes various learning effects: Through their involvement in the energy community, members learn a lot about the energy sector and how to develop and operate projects. This engagement raises their awareness.
- Energy communities may contribute to technological and social innovation.
- Not often discussed, but sometimes mentioned: Energy communities add another type of actor in the energy markets and strengthen competition.
- Even less studied: A higher diversity of actors may strengthen the resilience of the energy system.

Energy communities may help members and communities to **emancipate**:

- Politically – usually discussed under the terms “energy democracy” or “energy citizenship”.
- Socially – strengthened social cohesion as an effect of community engagement in the energy sector.
- Economically – higher regional or local value added and/or local development processes triggered by the activities of energy communities.
- Distributionally – if a REC can deliver electricity or heat at a lower price, especially to vulnerable households, it may contribute to combat energy poverty.

Energy communities may contribute to **legitimacy** of the energy transition and/or activities of specific businesses:

- Project-related social acceptance is said to be higher in case of community ownership (all else being equal).
- RECs may contribute to higher political acceptance and general acceptance of renewable energy technologies.
- Engaging in an energy community might help to form a positive image of a company (“license to operate”).

Figure 1: Overview of Impacts (Benefits and Costs) of Energy Communities Discussed in the Literature

3 Impacts of Energy Communities and Ways How to Assess Their Impacts

3.1 Effectiveness through Energy Communities

Empirical studies on effectiveness-related impacts of energy communities are listed in Table 1, grouped by type of method applied to assess these impacts (qualitative interviews, standardised surveys, models).

RECs invest into different energy transition projects and therefore contribute to reaching policy targets, e.g. for the share or volume of renewable energies. This effect could be measured in amount invested. If collected for several years, it needs to be deflated and discounted to current value. Net effects are calculated by deducting policy support through funding programmes dedicated to energy communities. Beyond this monetary aspect, stakeholders may also bring in space/land that would otherwise be hard to mobilise for the use of renewable energies. However, we have not come across a study directly measuring this impact.

Renewable energy projects reduce greenhouse gas emissions compared with the electricity or heating mix (as long as we have not yet reached a 100% renewables system). There are established methodologies in all EU MSs to account for these effects. The Austrian coordination office for energy communities [Österreichische Koordinationsstelle für Energiegemeinschaften] provides a calculation tool online (Energieinstitut Vorarlberg & Österreichische Koordinationsstelle für Energiegemeinschaften, 2022) and downloadable as MS Excel file (xlsx) (Österreichische Koordinationsstelle für Energiegemeinschaften, 2022), which includes a section on CO₂ emission reductions. In principle, this tool – i.e. the xlsx version of it – should be adaptable to other country contexts. Biodiversity or other environmental benefits are harder to calculate, which is why we have not come across any study empirically assessing them.

Decentralised generation of electricity from renewable sources and consumption close to generation reduces transmission losses that would have occurred with generation from centralised power plants. It may also prevent supra-regional grid bottlenecks. Further effects on grids, especially distribution lines, are controversial. Under certain circumstances, however, collective prosumers may help to reduce necessary grid extensions and investments also on this grid level.

There is a growing literature on the influence that participation in an energy community has on energy use behaviour. Some papers report increased energy savings. However, there may also be rebound effects at work, i.e. higher use of electricity (or heat) as a result of past savings and thus increased free income. More generally, being a member of an energy community could have an effect on lifestyles. However, this is harder to measure.

The increase in education through participation in RECs affects both increased environmental awareness and creation of expert knowledge, e.g. in the area of energy literacy. Expert knowledge can, in turn, have a positive impact on the local value-added creation within a community, e.g. through experience in the field of business management (see below).

Direct innovation effects have been intensively discussed for some sectors such as wind power in Denmark (Garud & Karnøe, 2003). RECs can act as positive change agents in the transition process. Increased political acceptance and new societal norms safeguard political and social processes. Overall, this helps to reach renewable energy and other policy targets.

Supporting RECs may strengthen competition. Again, this impact is hard to measure beyond market shares and indicators typically used in competition policy.

Lastly, RECs act differently from other energy market stakeholders. If RECs have a non-negligible share, this will contribute to a diversity of actors, which, in turn, may increase the ability of the energy system to react to shocks (“resilience”).

Table 1: Impacts of Energy Communities Related to Effectiveness

Impact	Known Effects	References
Mobilisation of Resources	Reach RE targets; share costs, improved project economics through cost savings or further business models, e.g., energy sharing	Interviews: [9,11,12,13,16,22,25,27,28,29,30,36,50,58] Surveys: [30,35,60] Models: [2,14,45,46,47,48,49,51,52,53,54,55] hypothetical → “potential” studies, see <i>Background Paper #3</i>
Environmental Effects	Reduction of greenhouse gas emissions, biodiversity Potential negative environmental effects, e.g. of wind turbines	Interviews: [7,12,17,18,19,36] Surveys: [2,17,23,35]
Grid Effects	Avoidance of grid transmission losses from central power plants Lower need for grid investments Reduction of grid bottlenecks	Interviews: [12,41,44] Models: [41,42,44]
Influence on Behaviour	Energy savings vs. rebound effects, on lifestyles	Interviews: [2,11,12,13,17,18,20,22,27,28,30,36,56] Surveys: [1,17,20,32,40,60]
Learning Effects	Increased awareness Higher energy literacy	Interviews: [2,4,9,11,12,13,20,21,24,25,26,27,28,29,30,36,57,58] Surveys: [20,30,32,35]
Innovation Effects	Reach RE targets; positive change agents, policy support, technological innovation (incl. reduced costs for PV, thriving PV market), new societal norms	Interviews: [7,57]
Strengthening Competition	Larger number of market players, esp. smaller players	Only theoretical: [37]
Resilience	Higher diversity of actors increases resilience of the system	Interview: [9] (resilience of local economy, not energy sector) Only theoretical: [37]

Source: Own compilation, partly based on Berka & Creamer (2018), extended and updated.

3.2 Emancipation through Energy Communities

Empirical studies on emancipation-related impacts of energy communities are listed in Table 2, grouped by type of method applied to assess these impacts (qualitative interviews, standardised surveys, models).

Some regard participation as a value by and in itself. Community ownership means that more people are directly involved in the energy sector, a fact often called “energy democracy” or, from the actors’ perspective, “energy citizenship”. However, the real level of participation in REC activities differs from energy community to energy community (Radtko, 2016). A simple indicator would be number of members. Borrowing from the literature on democracy measurement would be conceivable, but so far it is not to be found in the reviewed literature.

Working towards a common goal and participating in a renewable energy project strengthens regional or local cohesion within the community. Sense of community is not only a prerequisite for a successful energy community to be formed, but also a result of energy communities’ activities; it is reinforced by these activities. Again, quantification is difficult.

Municipalities benefit from the positive economic developments in the regions related to the use of RECs, which includes, among others, the creation of new jobs, increased local incomes from returns on investment and, above all, municipal tax revenues (Agentur für Erneuerbare Energien, n.d.). For Germany, these effects can be exemplarily demonstrated with the “value-added calculator” [Wertschöpfungsrechner], which has been developed by the Institute for Ecological Economy Research (IÖW) for the Renewable Energy Agency (AEE). The calculator represents a tool for municipal decision-makers to calculate the local value creation effects and potentials from different renewable energies (Agentur für Erneuerbare Energien, n.d.). Furthermore, it offers the possibility to calculate, for instance, tax revenues, company profits, income from employment and general effects of environmental protection measures and prepares forecasts of value added for the years 2025 and 2030 (Agentur für Erneuerbare Energien, n.d.). With regard to taxes, the calculator distinguishes between state, federal and municipal tax revenues (Heinbach et al., 2014). Raupach-Sumiya et al. test the transferability of the IÖW model to other countries, using Japan

as an example (Raupach-Sumiya et al., 2015). While they confirm the general results of analyses on the effect of community participation on local value added, their study also illustrates that several adaptations within the tool itself are necessary for such a transfer. This concerns not only the calculation of tax revenues due to different tax systems, but also the data basis regarding value chains and prices on which the calculations are based.

In some cases, energy communities contribute to addressing problems of energy poverty. This is obviously the case in (rural) electrification cases in the Global South, where energy communities help to connect households that previously had no access to electricity (Barroco Fontes Cunha et al., 2021; Holstenkamp, 2019; Joshi & Yenneti, 2020). However, the potential of energy communities for alleviating energy poverty is also discussed in the EU: Energy communities could provide access to affordable energy tariffs, e.g. through energy sharing, and to energy efficiency measures and information, which are offered to members (and sometimes non-members/the general public) (Hanke et al., 2021; Saintier, 2017). Moreover, by participating in an energy community energy poor might be activated and empowered (DellaValle & Czako, 2022). The topic could be generalised to social inclusion or even broader to energy justice. The question of representation is already somewhat included in the concept of “energy democracy” – if only selected, economically better-off people participated in democratic decision-making processes, this would not be called a “democracy”. Moreover, social inclusion is commonly subsumed as a dimension under the concept of justice. Hence, we use “energy justice” here.

Table 2: Impacts of Energy Communities Related to Emancipation

Impact	Known Effects	References
Energy Democracy/ Energy Citizenship	Higher level of participation	Interviews: [9,27,28]
		Surveys: [31]
Strengthening Civic Engagement	Social cohesion, sense of community	Interviews: [4,7,9,11,12,15,17,21,22,25,26,27,28,29,30,34,58]
		Surveys: [2,17,30,31,34,35]
Regional or Local Value Added & Regional Development	Job creation, tax revenues, local income; multiplier effects	Interviews: [9,11,12,13,16,22,25,27,28,29,30,50,58]
		Surveys: [30,35,60]
		Models: [2,14,38,39,45,46,47,48,49,51,52,53,54,55]
Energy Poverty Energy Justice	Partly: directly addressing energy poverty, access to affordable tariffs, empowering energy poor But: RECs not necessarily inclusive	Interviews: [13,20,27,28,30,33,43]
		Surveys: [1,20,33,60]

Source: Own compilation, partly based on Berka & Creamer (2018), extended and updated.

3.3 Legitimacy through Energy Communities

Empirical studies on legitimacy-related impacts of energy communities are listed in Table 3, grouped by type of method applied to assess these impacts (qualitative interviews, standardised surveys, models).

Increased project-related social acceptance is one of the main arguments used in political discourses to support energy communities. The literature shows that – all else being equal (“ceteris paribus”) – this seems to be (mostly) true if processes are designed in an inclusive manner. However, these findings are controversial. To summarise, community ownership seems to be beneficial, but is neither a necessary nor a sufficient condition for social acceptance. Moreover, we could not identify studies that measure the effect on social acceptance in terms of shorter project development duration or higher success rates.

Through learning effects as discussed above, RECs can influence the public's attitude towards renewable energy technologies and contribute to an increase in their acceptance. Moreover, acceptance among local politicians and authorities might be higher. We have not found a study empirically investigating these effects, though.

Lastly, the rationale for company members to participate in energy communities sometimes is to improve their image. Engaging in renewable energy developments lends them a green corporate image. While it might be relatively easy to identify motivations to participate, effects on companies' image is probably hard to measure as it is the result of not only the engagement in the energy community, but of all activities and other influencing factors.

Table 3: *Impacts of Energy Communities Related to Legitimacy*

Impact	Known Effects	References
Project-Related Social Acceptance	Increased social acceptance by local inhabitants	Interviews: [3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,59] Surveys: [2,6,17,60]
General and Project-Specific Political Acceptance	Increased acceptance of renewable energy technologies and among local politicians and authorities	(None identified)
Green Corporate Image	Positive image for (company) members	Interviews: [36]

Source: Own compilation, partly based on Berka & Creamer (2018), extended and updated.

4 Recommendations

In this document, we propose a typology of impacts – costs and benefits – that energy communities may have. Furthermore, we list several research articles that empirically investigate these impacts using various methods and foci regarding technology, geography or number of cases, to state just three dimensions according to which we can differentiate these studies. As Berka and Creamer (2018) highlight, there are many research gaps and shortcomings in the existing body of literature. These gaps are partly addressed by ongoing research projects. Therefore, we recommend to

- regularly update (and improve on) our overview, e.g. by collecting further information on listed and other studies through crowdsourcing, and
- further elaborate on different conceptualisations of these impact categories and their operationalisation in empirical investigations.

The overview of existing studies could become part of the European Energy Communities Repository. For this or other purposes, we provide our list of studies in different formats for the use in reference management software and as a text document, grouped according to impact categories and methods.

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Appendix – Literature Mentioned in the Tables

No	Source
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